

Resilience Requirements : Process Modeling Languages

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey.

This survey assesses the relevance of a set of requirements for process modeling languages to represent **resilience** characteristics of industrial systems.

Your responses will help us identify the requirements to define an *evaluation framework* aimed to support us in evaluating the ability of existing process modeling languages to represent resilience characteristics of industrial systems.

This research is part of an international project conducted by Luis Gustavo Nardin (luisgustavo.nardin@emse.fr), Khaled Medini (khaled.medini@emse.fr), and Mohamed Cheikh (cheikh.mohamed@emse.fr) from Mines Saint-Étienne (France), and Fabio Levy Siqueira (levy.siqueira@usp.br) from Universidade de São Paulo (Brazil).

The survey should take approximately 20–30 minutes to complete. All responses will be used solely for the purposes of this research.

There are 27 questions in this survey.

Profile

Please answer the following questions about you.

What is your primary role?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Academic/researcher
- Operations manager
- Process engineer
- Software engineer
- Systems engineer
- Student
- Other

In which industry do you primarily work or study?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Academia
- Automotive or aerospace
- Chemicals or pharmaceuticals
- Energy (oil & gas, power, renewables)
- Information technology
- Logistics or supply chain
- Manufacturing
- Other

How many years of experience do you have in modeling or working with industrial processes?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I don't have any experience
- Less than 1 year
- 1–2 years
- 3–4 years
- 5-10 years
- More than 10 years

I understand what resilience means in industrial processes.

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

I consider resilience an important requirement when modeling industrial processes.

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Do you agree with the following Resilience definition?

Resilience is the capability of systems to rapidly recover and restore normal operation after experiencing unexpected disruptions or adverse events.

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

What don't you agree with about this definition? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Strongly Disagree' or 'Undecided' or 'Disagree' at question ' [G01Q22]' (Do you agree with the following Resilience definition? Resilience is the capability of systems to rapidly recover and restore normal operation after experiencing unexpected disruptions or adverse events.)

Please write your answer here:

Disruption Representation and Severity

Consider the following requirement for a process modeling language to represent **resilience** of industrial systems:

Disruption Representation and Severity: The language should be able to explicitly represent disruptive events with varying severity and their potential effects on process flow.

About this requirement:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I clearly understand the description of this requirement.	<input type="radio"/>				
This requirement is important to represent resilience of industrial systems.	<input type="radio"/>				
This requirement can be used to evaluate a process modeling language.	<input type="radio"/>				

Do you have any suggestion regarding this requirement or its description?

Please write your answer here:

Stable and Dynamic Behavior Coexistence

Consider the following requirement for a process modeling language to represent **resilience** of industrial systems:

Stable and Dynamic Behavior Coexistence: The language should support the representation of both routine and predictable behaviors (e.g., fixed production flows) as well as adaptive and context-sensitive behaviors (e.g., rerouting in response to equipment failures or fluctuating demands).

About this requirement:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I clearly understand the description of this requirement.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement is important to represent resilience of industrial systems.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement can be used to evaluate a process modeling language.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you have any suggestion regarding this requirement or its description?

Please write your answer here:

Situation Awareness Representation

Consider the following requirement for a process modeling language to represent **resilience** of industrial systems:

Situation Awareness Representation: The language must provide constructs capable of explicitly representing internal system states, external environmental conditions, and timing aspects (e.g., delays or deadlines).

About this requirement:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I clearly understand the description of this requirement.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement is important to represent resilience of industrial systems.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement can be used to evaluate a process modeling language.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you have any suggestion regarding this requirement or its description?

Please write your answer here:

Exception and Interruption Handling

Consider the following requirement for a process modeling language to represent **resilience** of industrial systems:

Exception and Interruption Handling: The language must include explicit constructs for representing exceptions, faults, and interruptions, and the system responses when such conditions occur.

About this requirement:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I clearly understand the description of this requirement.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement is important to represent resilience of industrial systems.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement can be used to evaluate a process modeling language.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you have any suggestion regarding this requirement or its description?

Please write your answer here:

Human Intervention and Discretionary Control

Consider the following requirement for a process modeling language to represent **resilience** of industrial systems:

Human Intervention and Discretionary Control: The language must include constructs representing manual actions, user decisions, and tasks reliant on human judgment.

About this requirement:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I clearly understand the description of this requirement.	<input type="radio"/>				
This requirement is important to represent resilience of industrial systems.	<input type="radio"/>				
This requirement can be used to evaluate a process modeling language.	<input type="radio"/>				

Do you have any suggestion regarding this requirement or its description?

Please write your answer here:

Recovery and Transition to Normal Operation

Consider the following requirement for a process modeling language to represent **resilience** of industrial systems:

Recovery and Transition to Normal Operation: The modeling language must provide constructs to represent recovery phases, including criteria, conditions, and timing for transitioning back from degraded states to stable operations.

About this requirement:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I clearly understand the description of the requirement.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement is important to represent resilience.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement can be used to evaluate a process modeling language.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you have any suggestion regarding this requirement or its description?

Please write your answer here:

Learning, Adaptation, and Feedback Support

Consider the following requirement for a process modeling language to represent **resilience** of industrial systems:

Learning, Adaptation, and Feedback Support: The language must support adaptation over time, including feedback-driven updates and evolving logic.

About this requirement:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I clearly understand the description of this requirement.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement is important to represent resilience of industrial systems.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement can be used to evaluate a process modeling language.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you have any suggestion regarding this requirement or its description?

Please write your answer here:

Consider the following requirement for a process modeling language to represent **resilience** of industrial systems:

Complexity Management: The language must provide features to manage complexity, including modularity, hierarchical decomposition, abstraction mechanisms, or navigational support.

About this requirement:

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I clearly understand the description of this requirement.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement is important to represent resilience of industrial systems.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This requirement can be used to evaluate a process modeling language.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you have any suggestion regarding this requirement or its description?

Please write your answer here:

We have presented eight requirements for process modeling languages to represent resilience characteristics of industrial systems (see below). Do you think any requirement is missing?

1. **Disruption Representation and Severity:** The language should be able to explicitly represent disruptive events with varying severity and their potential effects on process flow.
2. **Stable and Dynamic Behavior Coexistence:** The language should support the representation of both routine and predictable operations (e.g., fixed production flows) and adaptive, context-sensitive behaviors (such as rerouting in response to equipment failures or fluctuating demands).
3. **Situation Awareness Representation:** The language should support the representation of both routine and predictable behaviors (e.g., fixed production flows) as well as adaptive and context-sensitive behaviors (e.g., rerouting in response to equipment failures or fluctuating demands).
4. **Exception and Interruption Handling:** The language must include explicit constructs for representing exceptions, faults, and interruptions, and the system responses when such conditions occur.
5. **Human Intervention and Discretionary Control:** The language must include constructs representing manual actions, user decisions, and tasks reliant on human judgment.
6. **Recovery and Transition to Normal Operation:** The modeling language must provide constructs to represent recovery phases, including criteria, conditions, and timing for transitioning back from degraded states to stable operations.
7. **Learning, Adaptation, and Feedback Support:** The language must support adaptation over time, including feedback-driven updates and evolving logic.
8. **Complexity Management:** The language must provide features to manage complexity, including modularity, hierarchical decomposition, abstraction mechanisms, or navigational support.

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

What requirements do you think are missing? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question ' [G10Q24]' (We have presented eight requirements for process modeling languages to represent resilience characteristics of industrial systems (see below). Do you think any requirement is missing? Disruption Representation and Severity: The language should be able to explicitly represent disruptive events with varying severity and their potential effects on process flow. Stable and Dynamic Behavior Coexistence: The language should support the representation of both routine and predictable operations (e.g., fixed production flows) and adaptive, context-sensitive behaviors (such as rerouting in response to equipment failures or fluctuating demands). Situation Awareness Representation: The language should support the representation of both routine and predictable behaviors (e.g., fixed production flows) as well as adaptive and context-sensitive behaviors (e.g., rerouting in response to equipment failures or fluctuating demands). Exception and Interruption Handling: The language must include explicit constructs for representing exceptions, faults, and interruptions, and the system responses when such conditions occur. Human Intervention and Discretionary Control: The language must include constructs representing manual actions, user decisions, and tasks reliant on human judgment. Recovery and Transition to Normal Operation: The modeling language must provide constructs to represent recovery phases, including criteria, conditions, and timing for transitioning back from degraded states to stable operations. Learning, Adaptation, and Feedback Support: The language must support adaptation over time, including feedback-driven updates and evolving logic. Complexity Management: The language must provide features to manage complexity, including modularity, hierarchical decomposition, abstraction mechanisms, or navigational support.)

Please write your answer here:

Do you have any additional suggestions?

Please write your answer here:

If you would like to receive the survey results, please include your e-mail address.

Please write your answer here:

Thank you for participating in this survey! Please contact us if you have any questions: Luis Gustavo Nardin (luisgustavo.nardin@emse.fr) or Fabio Levy Siqueira (levy.siqueira@usp.br).

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.